

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF MALL AND CALL IN LEARNING BIPA FOR INTERNATIONAL STUDENTS AT UNIVERSITAS MUHAMADIYAH PURWOKERTO (UMP), INDONESIA

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ABSTRACT

This research was motivated by the importance of proficiency on Indonesian language, especially for foreign/international students studying in Indonesia, especially at UMP. BIPA or (Indonesian Language for Non-Native Indonesian Speakers had important role for the students for mastering the language). One of supporting activities for studying Indonesian is CALL (Computer Assisted Language Learning) and MALL (Mobile Assisted language learning). This research aimed to figure out: a) effectiveness and frequency of CALL and MALL uses as a means of learning, and b) advantages and disadvantages of this learning. It was non-experimental research by using survey method/interview analysis by giving questionnaire to the students. It shows that most the international students tend to use MALL such as Google translate, YouTube, Mp3, and KBBi app. They considered to use MALL, because it was: 1) cheap and efficient, 2) fun, 3) free to learn Indonesian anytime, and 4) self-sufficient. It could be concluded that the use of MALL was effective for supporting the international students to learn Indonesian besides learning the language on BIPA program provided by the university.

DOI : 10.5281/zenodo.2540573

1. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, Indonesian language is increasingly in demand by foreigners. Many educational institutions that teach the language as a foreign language both in Indonesia and overseas. This Indonesian language learning for foreign speakers is intended to introduce Indonesian to foreign speakers for various purposes, both teaching and practical communication. In addition, learn Indonesian as a foreign language, like other languages as foreign languages, intended to provide verbal and written mastery to learners, as well as to provide verbal and written mastery to learners. This implies that they are expected to be able to use Indonesian to speak fluently and at the same time be able to understand the language spoken by the original speaker. (Wojowasito, 1977: 1-2).

BIPA in a higher institution in Indonesia is a language learning program designed for non-native speakers who are willing to learn Indonesian language (Bahasa Indonesia). It trains international students to actively communicate in written and spoken Indonesian. The program is also intended to introduce Indonesian culture and art to foreign speakers. Universitas Muhammadiyah Purwokerto (UMP) provides scholarships for BIPA courses for foreigners. Students who study at UMP for a certain time through student exchange programs or mobility programs. The participants do not only learn Indonesian but also Indonesian culture. The program also includes outdoor activities such as attending art workshops, field trips, and visiting cultural sites and tourist attractions. Song, and local musical instruments. In addition to travel packages to tourism places in Central Java and surrounding areas, participants have field trips to cultural sites, museums, health care centers, government offices, traditional markets and other institutions related to the topics given in the classes. After attending the course, students are expected to be

able to communicate naturally in Indonesian spoken and written both in formal and informal situations and to appreciate diversity of Indonesian cultures.

2. Variety of Media and Activities with BIPA Learners

a. Graphic Media

1. Picture / Photo
2. Sketch
3. Plan
4. Stringed Caricature
5. Poster
6. Map / Globe
7. Magazine
8. Newspapers

b. Media Audio

In this paper the factors that will be highlighted are the learning techniques used by BIPA teachers. Various and innovative learning techniques will arouse students' interest in the BIPA teaching and learning process. The learning technique referred to in this paper is an interactive language learning technique. Among groups that indirectly helped to spread the Indonesian language were students or students studying abroad. In addition, Indonesian workers and artists who work there also have the same role in this regard. Indonesian musicians who hold concerts abroad by singing their songs in Indonesian are able to arouse curiosity for the local community to find out the meaning so they are interested in learning Indonesian. For example, Anggun Cipta Sasmi, one of the Indonesian singers who has been worldwide. Although she has become a citizen of France, she often brings her songs in Indonesian in every appearance in European and American countries. CALL (Computer Assisted Language Learning) is the use of computers as a language learning aid. According to Turner & Taylor (2000), CALL has two broad categories, CALL that is "traditional and CALL that uses" generic (original) sources. Traditional CALLs are developed from computer-based learning and training designs that are widely known outside language teaching. To run this program, we need a computer plus a speaker and a CD-ROM for audio software. In the framework presented by the CALL AMES training program Victorias Computer Literacy Center (Corbel, 1998, quoted at Turner & Taylor, 2000), the traditional CALL offers software that is divided into three categories: the first category is software with a teaching approach, in which computers are designed to teach something. In this case, language lessons are seen not only cumulatively, building from the smallest to greater things but also collectively from the formal system, grammar, vocabulary, and pronunciation words that can be confronted separately (Corbel, 1999). This approach relies on computer consistency and "patience", repetition, explanation and student activities. With the presence of multimedia that provides greater storage facilities on CD-ROMs, students can enjoy more sophisticated interactions and responses when opening program packages such as Click into English and Planet English (Turner & Taylor, 2000). The second category is software with an exploratory approach. Where greater control is in the hands of students. In this case, language learning is seen as a complex part of the system. Language learning is treated as a process of discovery or investigation until the formation through hypothesis testing carried out by students themselves. With a very large data storage capacity on CD Rom, trials conducted by students can be stored first and reused until they find

the intended one. The third category is software for manipulating text, which consists of elements of research and other broader approaches. This approach sees language as an integrated system unit while the computer is a tool. Corbel (1999) says that learning with this approach is obtained through practice and play rather than instruction through practice and practice.

Mobile Assisted Language Learning (MALL) is all types of language learning that uses the help of devices that can be moved and performed and different from Computer Assistance Language learning. MALL, in this case, provides more opportunities for students to access applications continuously and spontaneously through the context of various contexts of use. use "(Kukulka-Hulme & Shield, 2008 as cited in Rahimi & Miri, 2014). Several types of devices that can be used are cellphones, laptops, and tablets. Of the various types of devices available, cellphones are one of the most widely used devices. used among students and students, the change from ordinary mobile phones to smart phones provides their own space in the field of education and language teaching. The complete functions of smart phones such as computers, telephones, cameras, data transfer devices, video and sound also make this device a learning tool efficient (Rahimi & Miri, 2014) Chinnery (2006) also mentions that mobile-assisted learning has many advantages and gives teachers access to authentic content, communicative language training, and task completion. Mobile Assisted Language Learning can help teachers and students in language classes to improve oral and written communication skills, one of which is by managing Use the application in the learning and teaching process.

This is why we study foreign students in learning Indonesian. It turned out that BIPA learning by Purwokerto students especially Muhammadiyah University of Purwokerto was also mixed with mobile devices and computers. To support Indonesian language learning activities there will be examined how effective this phenomenon is. By reviewing calls and malls in the process of learning Indonesian for foreign students.

2. LITERATURE STUDY

The purpose of the study is to find out how effective CALL and MALL is to Indonesian language learning towards foreign students. With this, many applications are used both in cellphones and computers. So that it helps foreign students communicate through the activities of writing, reading, speaking and listening.

BIPA According to Experts

The BIPA program is an Indonesian language learning whose subject is a foreign learner. BIPA looks more or focuses on its learners. People who are subject to BIPA are foreigners. So, Indonesian is a foreign language for BIPA learners. BIPA learning makes foreigners capable and mastering Indonesian language (Kusmiatun, 2016: 1).

The Indonesian government it self has aggressively sent many BIPA lecturers to various parts of the world for the last few years who are interested and need Indonesian language learning. One of the BIPA lecturers who had the opportunity to teach abroad was Prayitno Tri Laksono (29).

This Indonesian Language Lecturer at Malang Islamic University from July to December 2016 then had the opportunity to teach in Thailand. On this occasion they revealed how great Indonesian learning is in the white elephant country.

CALL is an acronym from Computer-Assisted Language Learning which means in Indonesian, Language Learning with Computer Assistance. CALL is the most accepted term in the wider community. In the foundation program, CALL will be used in a broad sense to refer to any effort involving computers in language teaching and learning. CALL began to spread in

several universities from small computers to the education system in the early 1980s. But CALL was first popularized by Levy in 1997 with the aim of dividing the computer based on the role of its function, namely as a teacher and as a tool. For example a Flashcard program or a set of other online grammar exercises that as a tool will also represent itself as a teacher because the computer is in some ways a teaching function.

CALL limits are institutional and functional. Institutional roles include teaching management, classroom management, language skills, and others. Functional roles include practitioners, developers, researchers, and trainers. Computer-assisted language learning (CALL) is an approach to teaching and learning where computers and computer-based resources such as the Internet are used to present, strengthen and assess the material to be studied. Usually includes substantial interactive elements. This also includes searching and investigating applications in language teaching and learning. [1] Except for self-study software, CALL is intended to complement face-to-face language instruction, not replace it. [2]

MALL is an approach to language learning that is assisted or enhanced through the use of handheld devices. MALL includes educational applications, eBooks and eLibraries, course management systems, audio, video and images, QR codes and social media. To understand where we are now, we have to look back when the MALL starts. MALL's history returned to 1972 when Alan Kay described Dynabook, a thin, light, handheld, personal handheld computer for children with a flat screen, a keyboard and a rechargeable battery. The model has never been released commercially. The MALL offers all students a range of unprecedented learning possibilities that develop beyond the limitations of traditional learning spaces. "MALLs can be successfully used outside the classroom, as well as in classrooms and resource-poor environments. The potential of MALL is very large and by studying this field, we can learn how to use it. However, there are many pitfalls along the way that we must realize. We will look at key aspects of language learning supported by cellular and examples of activities.

The MALL offers us great benefits from going beyond time and place, and thus allows us to interact with colleagues from other parts of the world, and access learning material. However, with new research at MALL, new techniques are implemented to make us benefit from this new device.

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3. RESEARCH METHODS

This study uses a qualitative method. The method used in this study is a qualitative-interpretive approach. Data in using interview and filling out questionnaires. The case study in this study will be used for learning phenomena in Indonesian through vocations and malls. The subjects involved in this study were 3 foreign students from Thailand. Namely UMP students consisting of the Center for Pharmacy, PAI, and Psychology. In addition, data obtained from Thai students were 30 people, with 3 people to be interviewed and fill out questionnaires.

a. Research Limits

In this paper the researchers used qualitative research. Qualitative research (including historical and descriptive research) is research that does not use mathematical, statistical or computer models. The method used is the method used to provide information and argumentation.

Qualitative methods for using several forms of collection data such as open interview transcripts, descriptions of observations, and analysis of documents and other artifacts. The data is analyzed while maintaining the authenticity of the text that means it. This is done because the purpose of qualitative research is to understand phenomena from the perspective of participants, social and institutional contexts. So that a qualitative approach is generally inductive.

The population of foreign students in the UMP is 50 people, with total foreign students totaling 25 people. Then we only interviewed and gave questionnaires to 3 Thai foreign students from the faculties of PAI, PHARMACEUTICAL AND PSYCHOLOGY. In addition, the student level starts from semester 2 and semester 8.

c. Research limitations

In conducting this research, we did use the word international, but because of the unavailability of time only for students from Thailand.

Table 1 Thai students from PAI faculty

NO	Question	Never	Rarely	Often
1.	Do you use Mall in Indonesian learning?	-	-	√
2.	Do you use Call in Indonesian learning?	-	√	-
3.	Are there applications other than the Call and Mall that you use?	-	√	-

4. What applications are in the Call and Mall in learning Indonesian?

Answer: "Google translate, YouTube, mp3, KBBI 5.

5. What are the shortcomings and advantages of the Call and Mall applications?

Answer: "in Google translate when translating Indonesian into Thai language must be left first, when the result is not, the results will be confused / incorrect. In addition, in the KBBI application, there is no vowel pronunciation.

From the results of this study indicate that foreign students in learning Indonesian tend to use MALL more. Such applications that are very easy to download are Google translate, YouTube, and KBBI 5. These applications are very helpful in the Indonesian language learning process for foreign students. In addition to portable mobile phones everywhere, the reach of the internet is easy to find just like in a campus environment that has free Wi-Fi. With this in mind foreign students will be helped to communicate in teaching and learning activities, buying and selling, and other interactions. The advancement of the era provides convenience to mankind, as well as Google technology that has the automatic translator of various Google Translate languages. Its existence as an online English translator application has proven to shift the habits of many people who previously had to open a dictionary to translate vocabulary, now just typing it, the meaning of each word automatically appears from various languages. Google translate is indeed widely used by foreign students, especially students from Thailand. In the process of

translating from Indonesian directly into Thai the results will be ambiguous. Therefore foreign students must first translate into English, then to Thai.

In the BIPA learning process, a lot of BIPA learning media, one of which is that can be used to simplify teaching Indonesian to foreigners. With these media, learners find it easier to learn Indonesian when compared without using media. The thing that we must pay attention to is learning does not experience difficulties in using the media.

BIPA Program and study period:

1. Regular program Levels 1-7 (3 months)

The regular level 1 - 7 BIPA program takes about three months (100 hours) per level and runs anytime as requested. Classes are scheduled for five days a week: Monday to Friday from 9am - 11am or from 1pm to 3pm. Language skills taught include speaking, reading, listening, writing, and building vocabulary using authentic BIPA materials and based on the Indonesian Language Course curriculum from the Ministry of Education and Culture. The program also includes art workshops, field trips and trips.

2. Short visit program (1 month)

A short visit program takes one month and runs at any time as requested. Classes are scheduled for five days a week: Monday to Friday from 9am - 11am or from 1pm to 3pm. Language skills taught include speaking, reading, listening, writing, and building vocabulary using authentic BIPA material. The program also includes art workshops, field trips and trips.

4. Special Program (2 weeks)

A special program with a fieldtrip takes two weeks and runs anytime as requested. Classes are scheduled for five days a week: Monday to Friday starting at 9 am 11 am or from 1 pm to 3 pm. This program focuses on daily conversation exercises. The program also includes art workshops and fieldtrips.

Foreign diplomats and observers generally want to broaden their horizons and knowledge about Indonesia. Therefore, they need Indonesian language books that can provide complete information about Indonesia, including information about history, geography, anthropology, law, politics, economics, and culture. Similarly, foreign scholars who study Indonesia also need information about various aspects of Indonesian life in full because they want to study Indonesia as an object of regional study, including history, geography, anthropology, law, politics, economics and culture.

In using the KBBI application it is very helpful in Indonesian language learning for foreign students. Quite a lot of Indonesian dictionary applications for both Android and IOS. In this application it is very helpful in word processing, but this KBBI application has no effect vocal, so the reader can only understand in terms of writing. For example in the word "apple", students can interpret apples as fruit and apples as verb forms. But it can be ascertained, KBBI V is the best application to date. Besides being an official application issued by the Language Development and Development Agency, the Ministry of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia, KBBI V has various advantages. Not just giving the meaning of a word but equipped with various features that are very helpful. Some of these features include.

Search for words quickly and completely

Just type the word you want to search for meaning, and the KBBI application will present the meaning of the word quickly without loading. When typing a word is done, suggestions for other

related words will be displayed. In every word meaning that is displayed, also includes a link with various combinations of words, derivative words, and proverbs related to the word.

5. CONCLUSION

The conclusion as a result of the achievement of the target of using BIPA or (Indonesian for Non-Native Indonesian Speakers has an important role for students to master the language). One of the supporting activities for the Indonesian language study is CALL and MALL in the Indonesian language learning process for foreign students that is more effective in using MALL than using CALL. With a variety of applications used, such as Google Translate, YouTube, and KBBI 5. These applications are very influential in the effectiveness of Indonesian language learning for foreign students. This is independent of, achieved or not achieving a treatment target according to the definition of response. So that foreign students are able to open and express their thoughts in Indonesian in an atmosphere that is supportive and able to express themselves, both in terms of reading, listening, speaking and writing.

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